

UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI
DI MILANO

UNIVERSITÀ
DI TORINO

ivia
Institut Valencià
d'Investigacions Agràries

SWRI
Soil and Water Resources Institute

External Scientific Report

PPP exposure models for 3D orchards considering spraying technologies in Southern Europe

Giovanna Azimonti¹, Patricia Chueca Adell², Konstantinos P. Ferentinos³, Cruz Garcerá Figueroa², Marco Grella⁴, Mara Luini¹, Paolo Marucco⁴, Eric Mozzanini⁴, Marco Resecco⁴, Luca Tosti¹

¹ International Centre for Pesticides and Health Risk Prevention-ASST Fatebenefratelli Sacco-
Department of Biomedical and Clinical Sciences, University of Milan, Italy.

²Centro de Agroingeniería Instituto Valenciano de Investigaciones Agrarias (IVIA), Valencia, Spain.

³Hellenic Agricultural Organization "DIMITRA" / Institute of Soil & Water Resources / Dept. of
Agricultural Engineering (ELGO-DIMITRA), Athens, Greece.

⁴University of Turin (UNITO) - Department of Agricultural, Forest and Food Sciences (DiSAFA),
Grugliasco, Italy.

APPENDIX F – Orchards images

Table of contents

Appendix F – 3D-orchards images.....	3
F.1. Vineyards.....	3
F.2. Olives	5
F.3. Citrus	6
F.4. Fruit orchards	7

Appendix F – 3D-orchards images

F.1. Vineyards

Vineyard (traditional) in SPAIN

Vineyard (Pergola trained) in ITALY

Vineyard (espalier trained) in ITALY

Vineyard (Alberello trained) in ITALY

3D-orchards – Appendix D

Vineyard (Geneva Double Curtain trained) IT

Vineyard (Tendone trained) in ITALY

Vineyard in GREECE

Vineyard in GREECE

F.2. Olives

Olive (semi-intensive) in SPAIN

Olive (traditional, extensive) in SPAIN

Olive (traditional, extensive) in ITALY

Olive (semi-intensive) in ITALY

www.efsa.europa.eu/publications

Olive (superintensive) in ITALY

EFSA Supporting publication

F.3. Citrus

Mandarine in SPAIN

Orange in SPAIN

Orange in ITALY

Orange in GREECE

www.efsa.europa.eu/publications

3D-orchards – Appendix D

F.4. Fruit orchards

Persimmon in SPAIN

Pomegranate in SPAIN

Two different types of peaches in SPAIN

Peach in ITALY

3D-orchards – Appendix D

Hazelnuts in ITALY

Walnut in GREECE

Pomegranate in GREECE

Peach in GREECE

3D-orchards – Appendix D

Fig in GREECE